

Volatile and monomeric tetranuclear lanthanide-zirconium isopropoxides

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Abstract : Volatile, hydrocarbon soluble, and monomeric derivatives of lanthanides and yttrium (abbreviated collectively as Ln) of the type $\text{LnZr}_3(\text{OPr}^i)_{15}$, where Ln = Y (1), La (2), Pr (3), Nd (4), Eu (5), Gd (6), Tb (7), Dy (8), Ho (9), Er (10), and Lu (11) have been prepared by the 1 : 3 reactions of $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ with $\text{K}\{\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_3\}$ in benzene. These novel compounds have been characterized by elemental and isopropoxo group analyses and molecular weight measurements as well as by their spectroscopic [IR, NMR (^1H and ^{13}C), electronic], and magnetic studies in suitable cases.

Keywords : Heterobimetallic isopropoxides, lanthanide-zirconium isopropoxides, pentaisopropoxozirconates.

Introduction

Many interesting aspects of lanthanide heterometallic alkoxide chemistry have been investigated¹⁻³ during the past four decades. After the discovery of technologically important mixed-metal oxide based superconducting materials^{4,5} such as $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{M}_x\text{CuO}_4$ (M = Sr, Ba; x = 0.15) and $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ (x = 0.19), respectively in 1986 and 1987, there has been unprecedented quest for novel class of heterometallic alkoxides of lanthanides. Other reasons for enhanced activity in heterometallic alkoxide chemistry of lanthanides include (i) the emergence of some intriguing reactivity⁶⁻⁸, (ii) diversity in structural features^{1-3,7-12}, (iii) introduction of nonaisopropoxidozirconate^{3,13}, $\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_9\}^-$, as a chelating ligand, and (iv) use of hetero bi- and -poly-metallic alkoxides as single-source precursors for the synthesis of nanocrystalline¹⁴ ceramic and magnetic materials.

In this paper, we report a systematic and detailed account of the synthesis and characterization of volatile, hydrocarbon soluble, and monomeric derivatives of the type $[\text{LnZr}_3(\text{OPr}^i)_{15}]$. This investigation assumes special significance as it provides a convenient route to a new type of isopropoxozirconates of the lanthanides to be used in future as potential precursors for the preparation of ultra-homogeneous mixed-metal oxide ceramics containing a lanthanide (Ln) and zirconium in 1 : 3 ratio by sol-gel and MOCVD processes.

Experimental

Rigorous exclusion of moisture was maintained throughout all the experimentations, handling, storage, and manipulations. Methods used for the purifications and drying of solvents, preparation of $\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_8(\text{Pr}^i\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ were similar to those already described in some of our earlier publications^{13,15}.

For metal estimations in the new derivatives, the compounds were hydrolyzed and dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and then zirconium was precipitated from the resulting acidic solution as zirconium mandelate and estimated as ZrO_2 after ignition¹⁶. From the filtrate obtained after filtration and washing the precipitate, yttrium and lanthanides were precipitated as oxalates and estimated as Ln_2O_3 after ignition¹⁶. Estimation of isopropoxo groups was carried out by oxidimetric method¹⁷.

IR spectra ($4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the new compounds were recorded as Nujol mulls on Perkin-Elmer 557 and Nicolet Magna 550 spectrophotometers using CsI optics. NMR spectra ^1H (89.55 MHz, CDCl_3) and ^{13}C (22.49 MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3/\text{C}_6\text{H}_6/\text{CCl}_4$) were recorded on a JEOL FX 90Q spectrometer. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Gouy balance. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene using Gallenkamp ebulliometer with thermister

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sensing device. Electronic spectra of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Ho^{III}, and Er^{III} derivatives were recorded in benzene solution on a Cary 50 Bio spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of pentaisopropoxozirconates of yttrium and lanthanides :

Due to similarity in the synthetic procedures, details of only one typical derivative [Tb{Zr(OPrⁱ)₅}₃] (7) are given below :

A benzene (~25 ml) solution of K{Zr(OPrⁱ)₅} [freshly prepared by the reaction of K (0.33 g, 8.44 mg atom) with isopropyl alcohol (~5 ml) in benzene (~20 ml) followed by addition of Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (3.25 g, 8.40 mmol) and refluxing the reaction mixture for ~3 h as well as removal of the volatiles] was added to a prestirred suspension of TbCl₃.3PrⁱOH (1.24 g, 2.79 mmol) in benzene (~30 ml). The reaction mixture after refluxing for 5 h was allowed to cool to room temperature. The precipitated KCl (0.63 g, 8.46 mmol) was filtered out and volatile components from the filtrate were removed under reduced pressure to afford off-white solid of composition TbZr₃(OPrⁱ)₁₅ (3.50 g, 95%), which was sublimed in an analytically pure state at 235 °C/0.2 mm in 75% yield.

Analytical details and some physical properties of all the new derivatives are summarized in Table 1.

Using a procedure similar to that employed for (7), the other derivatives (1)-(6) and (8)-(11) were also prepared. The amount of reactants actually used are shown in square brackets against each compound listed below :

(1) : YCl₃.3PrⁱOH [1.58 g, 4.21 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.49 g, 12.53 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (4.90 g, 12.65 mmol)]. (2) : LaCl₃.3PrⁱOH [2.04 g, 4.79 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.56 g, 14.32 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (5.60 g, 14.45 mmol)]. (3) : PrCl₃.3PrⁱOH [1.39 g, 3.29 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.38 g, 9.72 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (3.76 g, 9.71 mmol)]. (4) : NdCl₃.3PrⁱOH [1.39 g, 3.24 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.38 g, 9.72 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (3.76 g, 9.71 mmol)]. (5) : EuCl₃.3PrⁱOH [0.95 g, 2.16 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.25 g, 6.60 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (2.52 g, 6.50 mmol)]. (6) : GdCl₃.3PrⁱOH [1.22 g, 2.75 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.32 g, 8.33 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (3.20 g, 8.25 mmol)]. (8) : DyCl₃.3PrⁱOH [0.64

g, 1.42 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.17 g, 4.35 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (1.66 g, 4.28 mmol)] (9) : HoCl₃.3PrⁱOH [1.65 g, 3.66 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.43 g, 11.0 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (4.25 g, 10.97 mmol)]. (10) : ErCl₃.3PrⁱOH [0.94 g, 2.07 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.24 g, 6.29 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (2.42 g, 6.24 mmol)] (11) : LuCl₃.3PrⁱOH [1.22 g, 2.64 mmol] and KZr(OPrⁱ)₅ prepared from [K (0.31 g, 7.92 mg atom) + Zr(OPrⁱ)₄.PrⁱOH (3.07 g, 7.93 mmol)].

Results and discussion

Novel tetranuclear homoleptic heterobimetallic isopropoxides of lanthanides of the type LnZr₃(OPrⁱ)₁₅ (where Ln = a lanthanide and yttrium) have been prepared according to the following three sequential reactions (eqs. 1, 2 and 3) :

where Ln = Y (1), La (2), Pr (3), Nd (4), Eu (5), Gd (6), Tb (7), Dy (8), Ho (9), Er (10), and Lu (11)

These derivatives (Table 1) are highly moisture-sensitive, hydrocarbon soluble, monomeric, and volatile soft solids of different colours depending upon 4fⁿ configuration of the metal (Ln).

The identity of the new compounds described herein is corroborated by unchanged analytical and molecular weight data even after their volatilization under reduced pressure.

Table 1 Analytical and some physical data for tris(pentaisopropoxozirconato) lanthanide(III) and yttrium(III)

Compd. ^a	Colour	Volatility ^b (°C/mm)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)
			Ln	Zr	OPr ⁱ	
1	White	238/0.3 (65%)	7.0 (7.1)	22.1 (21.9)	70.6 (70.9)	1260 (1248)
2	White	210/0.05 (80%)	10.5 (10.7)	21.3 (21.1)	67.9 (68.1)	1290 (1298)
3	Green	240/0.4 (75%)	10.8 (10.7)	21.3 (21.1)	67.9 (68.1)	1285 (1299)
4	Blue	246/0.4 (72%)	11.0 (11.1)	21.2 (21.0)	67.7 (67.9)	1325 (1303)
5	White	220/0.2 (70%)	11.5 (11.6)	20.8 (20.9)	67.5 (67.6)	1328 (1312)
6	Light brown	223/0.2 (72%)	12.0 (11.9)	20.7 (20.8)	67.1 (67.3)	1348 (1317)
7	Off-white	230/0.2 (71%)	12.0 (12.0)	20.6 (20.7)	67.1 (67.2)	1329 (1319)
8	White	212/0.05 (78%)	12.3 (12.3)	20.6 (20.7)	66.9 (67.0)	1311 (1323)
9	Light yellow	250/0.3 (70%)	12.3 (12.5)	21.4 (21.6)	66.8 (66.9)	1342 (1324)
10	Pinkish-white	230/0.2 (75%)	12.7 (12.6)	20.5 (20.6)	66.6 (66.8)	1344 (1327)
11	White	248/0.4 (60%)	13.1 (13.0)	20.8 (20.5)	66.2 (66.4)	1351 (1334)

^aAll are waxy solids. ^bSublimed under reduced pressure. ^cRefers to the sublimed product.

Spectral and magnetic studies :

Infrared spectral data (Table 2) of the new compounds exhibit metal-oxygen stretching frequencies in the regions (in cm^{-1}) : 450–390 $\nu(\text{Ln-O})$ and 560–520 $\nu(\text{Zr-O})$. The $\nu(\text{C-O})$ and $\nu(\text{OPr}^i)$ absorptions are observed in the ranges 1020–930 and 1175–1120 cm^{-1} , respectively. All these assignments have been made by comparison with published data^{2,13,15,18} on metal alkoxides.

The room temperature ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3 solutions of the diamagnetic derivatives :

(1) : [1.21d (J 6.5 Hz) OCHMe_2 ; 4.28m (J 6.5 Hz) OCHMe_2], (2) : [1.19d (J 6.5 Hz) OCHMe_2 ; 4.12m (J 6.5 Hz) OCHMe_2] and (11) : [1.22d (J 6.4 Hz) OCHMe_2 ; 4.23m (J 6.4 Hz) OCHMe_2] are deceptively simple due to the fluxional behaviour of these molecules on NMR time scale, exhibiting only a doublet and a septet in the regions δ 1.10–1.25 and 4.10–4.30, respectively due to *gem*-dimethyl and methine protons of the isopropoxo groups.

Table 2. Infrared spectral data (cm^{-1}) for the new derivatives $\text{LnZr}_3(\text{OPr}^i)_5$

Compd.	$\nu(\text{C-O}); \nu(\text{OPr}^i)$	$\nu(\text{Zr-O})$	$\nu(\text{Ln-O})$
1 Ln	940m, 1000m; 1115m, 1150s	550m	405m, 440m
2 La	945m, 1000m; 1115m, 1150s	555m	405m, 455m
3 Pr	930s, 1000s; 1115s, 1160m	540m	430m
4 Nd	940m, 1000s; 1115m, 1150s	550m	390m, 440m
5 Eu	941m, 1007s; 1129s, 1161s	558m	407m, 422m
6 Gd	942m, 1014m; 1117m, 1162m	544m	395m, 430m
7 Tb	966s, 1014s; 1129s, 1173s	519m	414s
8 Dy	955m, 1000s; 1115s, 1158s	551m	410m
9 Ho	956m, 1002s; 1118s, 1156s	546m	409m
10 Er	955m, 1014m; 1125m, 1162m	558m	400m
11 Lu	940m, 1000s; 1115m, 1150s	550m	400w, 450m

^aAbbreviations : s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

Interestingly, the paramagnetic praseodymium ($4f^2$) and neodymium ($4f^3$) derivatives 3 and 4 exhibit reasonably sharp signals with small paramagnetic shifts, and the coupling of the isopropoxo group proton resonances is

also observed. This coupling is unresolved in the spectrum of holmium ($4f^{10}$) derivative **8**, which displays large paramagnetic shift in signal positions and very broad lines.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra (δ , ppm) of **1** [26.30 (OCHMe₂), 68.67 (OCHMe₂)], **2** [26.16 (OCHMe₂), 68.87 (OCHMe₂)] and **11** [26.39 (OCHMe₂), 69.86 (OCHMe₂)] recorded in CDCl₃ solutions at room temperatures exhibit sharp resonances due to α - and β -carbons of the isopropoxo groups in their characteristic regions.

The observed room temperature (301 K) magnetic moment data for the new derivatives of trivalent lanthanides **3** ($4f^2$), **4** ($4f^3$), **5** ($4f^6$), **6** ($4f^7$), **7** ($4f^8$), **8** ($4f^9$), **9** ($4f^{10}$), and **10** ($4f^{11}$) are 3.55, 3.60, 3.50, 7.90, 9.52, 10.42, 10.38, and 9.52 B.M., respectively, which are in good agreement with the calculated values.

The electronic spectra (in benzene solution) of **3**, **4**, **9**, and **10** recorded in the range 200–800 nm at room temperature, exhibit a number of closely adjacent bands due to $f \rightarrow f$ transitions. Out of these the hypersensitive⁹ absorption bands helpful in indicating coordination environment around Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Ho^{III}, and Er^{III} complexes are 447 nm ($^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3P_2$) and 588 nm ($^3H_4 \rightarrow ^1D_2$) for **3**, 585 nm ($^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}$, $^2G_{7/2}$ pair) for **4**, 452 nm ($^5I_8 \rightarrow ^5G_6$, 5F_1 pair) for **9** and 378 nm ($^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{11/2}$) and 520 nm ($^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^2H_{11/2}$) for **10**. The oscillator strengths (P) and covalency parameters such as nephelauxetic (β), bonding ($b^{1/2}$) as well as percentage covalency (δ) for these derivatives are given below :

(**3**) : $P \times 10^6$, 11.92/9.44; β , 0.9966; $b^{1/2}$, 0.029; δ , 0.340; (**4**) : $P \times 10^6$, 27.32; β , 0.9821; $b^{1/2}$, 0.067; δ , 1.867; (**9**) : $P \times 10^6$, 28.52; β , 0.9954; $b^{1/2}$, 0.043; δ , 0.459; (**10**) : $P \times 10^6$, 45.33/19.44; β , 0.997; $b^{1/2}$, 0.027; δ , 0.30.

A comparison^{15c,d} of δ , P , and shapes of the hypersensitive absorption bands of compounds **3**, **4**, **9**, and **10** with their tetraisopropoxo aluminate analogues [Ln{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}₃]; for which an octahedral environment of isopropoxo groups around the lanthanide Ln = Er¹⁹ has been elucidated crystallographically, clearly support for an octahedral geometry for lanthanides in all of these freshly prepared new derivatives (**1-11**) (see Structure I, eq. 3). It is also noteworthy, that a structure, [η^4 -{Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₉}Ln(μ -OPrⁱ)₂Zr(OPrⁱ)₄], involving both lanthanides and zirconium in an octahedral (coordinatively

saturated) state is an other possibility. Furthermore, variation in structural feature on ageing² can not be ruled out.

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